

On Chromaticity of Wheels

Zainab Yasir Al-Rekaby, Abdul Jalil M. Khalaf

Abstract—Let the vertices of a graph such that every two adjacent vertices have different color is a very common problem in the graph theory. This is known as proper coloring of graphs. The possible number of different proper colorings on a graph with a given number of colors can be represented by a function called the chromatic polynomial. Two graphs G and H are said to be chromatically equivalent, if they share the same chromatic polynomial. A Graph G is chromatically unique, if G is isomorphic to H for any graph H such that G is chromatically equivalent to H . The study of chromatically equivalent and chromatically unique problems is called chromaticity. This paper shows that a wheel W_{12} is chromatically unique.

Keywords—Chromatic Polynomial, Chromatically Equivalent, Chromatically Unique, Wheel.

I. INTRODUCTION

A graph G is planar if it can be drawn in the plane with no crossing edges. A λ -coloring of a graph G is a mapping $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, \lambda\}$ such that: $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for every edge $uv \in E(G)$. A minimum number λ such that G has a proper coloring is called chromatic number, and G called λ -colorable. During their attempts to prove the four-color problem (Every planar graph is 4-colorable), Mathematicians found many useful tools for solving graph coloring problems. Birkhoff [1] proposed a way to attack the four-color problem by introducing a function $P(M, \lambda)$, the number of ways of proper λ -colorings of a map M . $P(M, \lambda)$ is a polynomial called chromatic polynomial of M . In 1968, Read [2] asked: What is a necessary and sufficient condition for two graphs to be chromatically equivalent; that is, to have the same chromatic polynomial?

Chao and Whitehead Jr. [3] defined a graph to be chromatically unique if no other graphs share its chromatic polynomial and another question appears: What is a necessary and sufficient condition for a graph to be chromatically unique?

Chromaticity, mean study of the above two questions of chromatically equivalent and chromatically unique.

During the period when the Four-Color Problem remained unsolved, which spanned more than a century, many approaches were introduced that would lead to a solution to this famous problem [4].

A wheel W_n is a graph of order n , where $n \geq 4$, obtained from cycle C_{n-1} by adding a new vertex w adjacent to each vertex of the cycle. Each edge incident with w is a spoke of

Z. Y. Al-Rekaby is with the Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Kufa, P.O. Box 21, Najaf, Iraq (e-mail: zainabyours@yahoo.com).

A. M. Khalaf is with the Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Kufa, P.O. Box 21, Najaf, Iraq (Corresponding author; e-mail: abduljaleel.khalaf@uokufa.edu.iq).

the wheel.

Xu and Li [5] proved that W_n , for odd $n \geq 5$ is chromatically unique. They also showed that W_8 is not chromatically unique. Chao and Whitehead demonstrated that W_6 is not chromatically unique while Read [2] discovered that W_{10} is chromatically unique. Later on Li and Whitehead Jr. [6] proved these results mathematically. This paper introduced mathematical proof of the chromatic uniqueness of W_{12} .

II. AUXILIARY RESULTS

In this section, some known results are introduced some known results that help in proving the main result.

Theorem 1. [7] Let G be a graph of order n and size m . Then $p(G, \lambda)$ is a polynomial of degree n . Moreover, if $(G, \lambda) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i \lambda^{n-i}$, then

- 1- all coefficients a_i are integers and alternate in sign;
- 2- (i) $a_n = 0$
 (ii) $a_0 = 1$
 (iii) $a_1 = -m$
 (iv) $a_2 = \binom{m}{2} - t_1(G)$
 (v) $a_3 = -\binom{m}{3} + (m-2)t_1(G) + t_2(G) - 2t_3(G)$

Result (v) in the above theorem was obtained by Farrell [8] who also provided in [8] an expression for

$$a_4 = \binom{m}{4} - \binom{m-2}{2}t_1(G) - \binom{t_1(G)}{2} - (m-3)t_2(G) + (2m-9)t_3(G) - t_4(G) - 6t_5(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) + 3t_8(G) \quad (1)$$

Theorem 2. Let G be a graph of order n and size m . Then

$$p(G, \lambda) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\sum_{r=0}^m (-1)^r N(k, r) \right) \lambda^k \quad (2)$$

where $N(k, r)$ denote the number of spanning subgraphs of G having exactly k components and r edges [7].

Theorem 3. [7] Let G be a K_r -gluing of graph G_1 and G_2 . Then

$$p(G, \lambda) = \frac{p(G_1, \lambda)p(G_2, \lambda)}{p(K_r, \lambda)} \quad (3)$$

Theorem 4. [7] Let G and H be two chromatically equivalent graphs then we have:

1. $|V(G)| = |V(H)|$
2. $|E(G)| = |E(H)|$
3. $\chi(G) = \chi(H)$
4. $t_1(G) = t_1(H)$
5. $t_2(G) - 2t_3(G) = t_2(H) - 2t_3(H)$
6. G is connected if and only if H is connected
7. G is 2-connected if and only if H is 2-connected
8. $g(G) = g(H)$
9. G and H have the same number of shortest cycles .

III. RESULTS

This section is devoted to prove the chromatic uniqueness of W_{12} .

Theorem 5. The wheel W_{12} is chromatically unique.

Proof:

$$p(W_{12}, \lambda) = \lambda(\lambda - 1)(\lambda - 2)(\lambda - 3)(\lambda^4 - 9\lambda^3 + 31\lambda^2 - 49\lambda + 31)(\lambda^4 - 7\lambda^3 + 19\lambda^2 - 23\lambda + 11) \quad (4)$$

Let G be a graph such that $p(G, \lambda) = p(W_{12}, \lambda)$.

From Theorem 4 we have the following conditions:

1. G has 12 vertices.
2. G has 22 edges.
3. G has 11 triangles.
4. $\chi(G) = 4$
5. G has no cut vertex since G is 2- connected by no.7 in Theorem 1.
6. Since G is connected then G has no vertex of degree 0.
7. G has no a vertex of degree 1, if G has a vertex of degree 1 then $(\lambda - 1)^2$ divide $p(G, \lambda)$ but this is not the case.
8. G has no degree 2 vertex which is a triangle, if G has degree 2 then $(\lambda - 2)^2$ divide $p(G, \lambda)$ but this is not the case.
9. G has no K_5 subgraph since $(\lambda - 4)$ does not divide $p(G, \lambda)$.
10. In [7], Farrell derived formulas for the coefficients of λ^{p-3} and λ^{p-4} in (H, λ) , where H is a graph with p vertices. Specializing these formulas to $p(G, \lambda) = p(W_{12}, \lambda)$.

The coefficients of λ^{p-3} is:

$$-\binom{m}{3} + (m - 2)t_1(G) + t_2(G) - 2t_3(G) \quad (5)$$

where, m : edges, $m = 22$

$$\begin{aligned} t_1(G) &= \binom{p}{3} \\ t_1(G) &= \binom{12}{3} \\ t_1(G) &= \frac{12!}{3!9!} \\ t_1(G) &= 220 \\ \binom{22}{3} &= 1540 \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$-(1540) + 4400 + t_2(G) - 2t_3(G)$$

Derive the d formula for the coefficient of λ^{p-3}

$$t_2(G) = 2t_3(G)$$

The coefficient of λ^{p-4} is:

$$\binom{m}{4} - \binom{m-2}{2}t_1(G) - \binom{t_1(G)}{2} - (m-3)t_2(G) + (2m-9)t_3(G) - t_4(G) - 6t_5(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) + 3t_8(G)$$

where,

$t_4(G)$: the number of pure pentagons C_5 .

$t_5(G)$: the number of K_5 subgraph.

$t_6(G)$: the number of 2-3 complete bipartite graphs .

$t_7(G)$: the number of 5-vertex wheels with one spoke deleted X_4 .

$t_8(G)$: the number of wheel W_5 .

$$\binom{22}{4} - \binom{22-2}{2}t_1(G) - \binom{t_1(G)}{2} - (22-3)t_2(G) + (2(22)-9)t_3(G) - t_4(G) - 6t_5(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) + 3t_8(G)$$

$$\binom{22}{4} = 7315$$

$$t_5(G) = \binom{12}{5}$$

$$t_5(G) = 792$$

$$\binom{20}{2} = 190$$

$$(7315) - (190)(220) - \binom{220}{2} - (22-3)t_2(G) + (2(22)-9)t_3(G) - t_4(G) - 6(792) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) + 3t_8(G)$$

Derive the d formula for the coefficient of λ^{p-4}

$$-19t_2(G) + 35t_3(G) - t_4(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) + 3t_8(G) = 0 \quad (6)$$

11. G has no pure W_5 subgraph.

It is assumed that G contains a pure W_5 subgraph which implying that G contains a pure C_4 subgraph and a K_4 subgraph by (5). To consider various ways that the W_5 and K_4 subgraphs can overlap see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The different ways of W_5 and K_4 subgraphs are overlapping

$$p(G, \lambda) = \lambda(\lambda - 1)(\lambda - 2)^2(\lambda - 3)^2(\lambda^2 - 5\lambda + 7)(\lambda^2 - 3\lambda + 3)^2$$

This is contradiction with equation (A) :

$$t_2(G) = 2t_3(G) \text{ and } p(G, \lambda) \text{ not equal to } p(W_{12}, \lambda) .$$

12. G has no K_4 subgraphs.

According to (6) this condition is equivalent to the statement G has no C_4 subgraphs.

Since G has no pure W_5 subgraph from (8) then $t_8(G) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} t_2(G) &= 2t_3(G) \\ -19t_2(G) + 35t_3(G) - t_4(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) &= 0 \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Put (6) in (7):

$$\begin{aligned} -19(2)t_3(G) + 35t_3(G) - t_4(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) &= 0 \\ -38t_3(G) + 35t_3(G) - t_4(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) &= 0 \\ -3t_3(G) - t_4(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) &= 0 \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

K_4 be overlap with X_4 . We suppose that $t_3(G) = 1$ and $t_7(G) = 1$ then :

- Case 1. $t_3(G) = 1, t_7(G) = 1, t_4(G) = 0$ and $t_6(G) = 1$. The vertices are equal to 9 not 12, which is a contradiction.
- Case 2. $t_3(G) = 1, t_7(G) = 1, t_4(G) = 1$ and $t_6(G) = 2$. The triangles are equal to 9 not 11, which is a contradiction.
- Case 3. $t_3(G) = 1, t_7(G) = 1, t_4(G) = 2$ and $t_6(G) = 3$
- Case 4. The vertices must be greater than 12. Then the graph has no K_4 .

13. G has no separating edge (K_2 -gluing). It is assumed that G consists of two subgraphs G_1 and G_2 which overlap in a separating edge and two cases are considered:

- Case 1. G_1 and G_2 both contain odd cycles.
- Case 2. Only G_1 or G_2 contain odd cycles.

Both cases shows contradiction.

14. G has no a pure C_5 subgraph.

Since G has no pure W_5 subgraph from (8) then $t_8(G) = 0$.

Since G has no K_4 subgraph from (9) then $t_3(G) = 0$ and G has no C_4 subgraph from (9) then $t_2(G) = 0$.

Then:

$$\begin{aligned} -t_4(G) + t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) &= 0 \\ t_4(G) &= t_6(G) + 2t_7(G) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

All possible cases leads to contradiction.

15. G has no pure C_6 subgraph.

Since G has no W_5, K_4, C_4 and C_5 subgraphs then it is supposed that G has triangles with C_6 . (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 G has no pure C_6

However, this graph must contain a K_4 subgraph. Therefore, G has no pure C_5 subgraph.

16. G has no pure C_7 subgraph.

Since G has no W_5, K_4, C_4, C_5 and C_6 subgraphs then it is supposed that G has triangles with C_7 see Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 G has no pure C_7

But this graph must contain K_4 subgraph. Therefore, G has no pure C_7 subgraph.

17. G has no a pure C_8 subgraph.

Since G has no W_5, K_4, C_4, C_5, C_6 and C_7 subgraphs then it is supposed that G has triangles with C_8 . See Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 G has no pure C_8

This graph must contain a K_4 subgraph. Therefore, G has no pure C_8 subgraph.

Since G is a 2-connected graph without separating edges and G satisfies the conditions then G is isomorphic to W_{12} .

IV. CONCLUSION

It is not easy to prove the chromatic uniqueness of a certain graph. In this paper, it is concluded that the graph W_{12} is chromatically unique.

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Zainab Al-Rekaby completed B. Sc with Mathematics from the Faculty of Science, University of Kufa. Currently she is a master student in Graph Theory under the supervision of Assistant. Professor Dr. Abdul Jalil M. Khalaf. Her area of research is Graph polynomials and Graph colorings. In the area of graph coloring. she focuses on the chromaticity of graphs.

Abdul Jalil M. Khalaf has obtained his B.Sc. and M.Sc. in Mathematics from the College of Science, University of Mosul, and awarded a Ph.D. and Post Doctorate in Graph Theory from UPM. He is an editor and reviewer for many international journals. He is a member of American Society of Mathematics and senior member of the International Association of Computer Science and Information Technology.

Dr. Khalaf is Assistant Professor and head of Mathematics Department at the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Kufa.